

ISic3456

I.Sicily inscription 3456

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

rock

face

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Menae

Place of origin (modern)

Mineo

Provenance

rock face, contrada Papajanni, territory of Mineo

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Mineo, in situ

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text**Apparatus****Translation****Commentary****Digital identifiers:**

TM 491433

EDCS 55702039

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 2009.0441

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum*

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Rizzone, V.G. 2009. Iscrizioni tardoantiche da Mineo (CT). *Epigraphica*. 71: 426-437. At 436-437 no.4 fig.6

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